

ENCOURAGING TOURISM DEVELOPMENT THROUGH VIDEO GAMES

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Abstract. This present study investigated how the usage of video games affects tourism. The importance of video games in the field of tourism is that, nowadays, the number of tourists is increasing rapidly, which can lead to problems in navigational systems, obtaining accurate information about historical destinations or attractions, or dissatisfaction with museums. Besides that, there are many cultural destinations that need to be encouraged among tourists. Video games can increase people's interest in world touristic places and encourage them to travel by providing them with exact information and a correct overview of cities. Creating real-world maps based on video games can be the solution to these problems. With the help of such video games, players can learn the layout of some historical and cultural cities, and tourists can also acquire more information before visiting the places they want to see. In the case of Uzbekistan, incorporating the maps of famous tourist destinations into video games would be one of the best advertisements for foreigners to visit the country. This can impact the local economy by creating jobs and attracting visitors. Cities hosting game events benefit from increased tourism spending on accommodations, dining, entertainment, and merchandise. Moreover, video games can serve as a tool for cultural exchange, allowing players to experience different cultures and perspectives through gameplay. Real-world map-based video games could create significant opportunities for tourism in the territory of Uzbekistan, as these video games could serve as encyclopedias about the history and culture of Uzbekistan for tourists.

Keywords: Video games, cultural destinations, tourism, maps.

Аннотация. Анализ исследования посвящен влиянию использования видеоигр на туризм. Значимость видеоигр в области туризма заключается в том, что в настоящее время количество туристов стремительно растет, что может привести к проблемам в навигационных системах, получении точной информации о исторических достопримечательностях или объектах, а также к недовольству музеями. Кроме того, существует множество культурных направлений, которые необходимо привлекать к туристам. Видеоигры могут повысить интерес людей к мировым туристическим местам и побудить их к путешествиям, предоставляя точную информацию и правильное представление о городах. Создание видеоигр на основе реальных карт мира может стать решением этих проблем. С помощью таких видеоигр игроки могут изучить план некоторых исторических и культурных городов, а туристы также могут получить дополнительную информацию перед посещением интересующих их мест. В случае с Узбекистаном интеграция карт знаменитых туристических направлений в видеоигры станет одним из лучших рекламных средств для привлечения иностранцев в страну. Это может оказать влияние на местную экономику за счет создания рабочих мест и привлечения посетителей. Города, организующие игровые мероприятия, получают выгоду от увеличения расходов туристов на проживание, питание, развлечения и товары. Более того, видеоигры могут служить инструментом культурного обмена, позволяя игрокам испытывать различные культуры и точки зрения через игровой процесс. Видеоигры на основе реальных карт мира могут создать значительные возможности для развития туризма на территории Узбекистана,

поскольку эти видеоигры могут служить энциклопедиями о истории и культуре Узбекистана для туристов.

Ключевые слова: Видеоигры, культурные направления, туризм, карты.

Annotatsiya. Bu tadqiqot video o'yinlarning turizmga ta'siri qanday ekanligini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Video o'yinlarning turizm sohasida ahamiyati shundaki, bugungi kunda turistlar soni jadal ravishda oshmoqda, bu esa navigatsiya tizimlarida muammolar, tarixiy joylar haqida aniqlikka erishish yoki muzeylarda xatoliklar sodir bo'lishiga olib kelishi mumkin. Bundan tashqari, turistlar o'rtasida rag'batlantirilishi kerak bo'lgan ko'plab madaniy manzaralar mavjud. Video o'yinlar odamlarning dunyo turizm joylariga qiziqishini oshirib, ularni shaharlar haqida to'g'ri ma'lumotlar olishiga va shaharlar haqida to'g'ri tasavvur hosil qilishiga yordam berib, sayohatlar sonini oshirishi mumkin. Video o'yinlarga asoslangan haqiqiy jahon xaritalari bu muammolarga yechim bo'lishi mumkin. Ular orqali o'yinchilar ba'zi tarixiy va madaniy shaharlarning joylashuvini o'rganishlari mumkin bo'ladi, shuningdek, turistlar sayohat qilishlari kerak bo'lgan joylariga sayohat qilishdan oldin ko'proq ma'lumotlarga ega bo'ladi. O'zbekistondagi holatda mashhur turistik manzaralarining xaritalarini video o'yinlarga integratsiyalash, mamlakatga yangi sayohatchilarni jalb qilishni eng yaxshi usuli bo'lishi mumkin. Bu mahalliy iqtisodiyotda yangi ish o'rinlari yaratish va turistlarni jalb qilish orqali unga ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin. O'yin tadbirlariga mezbon qiluvchi shaharlar tashrif buyuruvchilarga mehmonxona, ovqatlanish joylari, ko'ngil ochar joylar va boshqa sharoitlarni yaratish orqali o'zlarining ekonomikalariga foyda olib kelishlari mumkin. Bundan tashqari, video o'yinlar madaniyatlar almashuvi uchun vosita sifatida xizmat qilishi mumkin, o'yinchilar o'yin orqali turli madaniyat va an'analarni ko'rishlari mumkin. Haqiqiy dunyo xaritalariga asoslangan video o'yinlar O'zbekiston hududida turizmida katta imkoniyatlar yaratishi mumkin, chunki bu video o'yinlar turistlar uchun O'zbekiston tarixi va madaniyatining ensiklopediyasi sifatida xizmat qilishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: Video o'yinlar, madaniy manzilar, turizm, xaritalar.

Encouraging Tourism Development through Video Games

Playing video games and spending time online have become globalized activities among people of all ages, from the younger generation to adults and the elderly. In today's evolving cyberspace, the entertainment industry, particularly video games, contributes significantly to the advancement of technology. As Eskidemir (2010) discovered, urban planning plays a crucial role in creating video game environments that incorporate real cities and settlements into their level design. A key technique employed in video game design to immerse players involves replicating the layout of the physical world with remarkable precision in the virtual environment. Video game development companies often utilize fictional and real-world settings, including maps, constructions, historical narratives, and local stories, to enhance the appeal and authenticity of their products. This approach extends players' imagination, allowing them to experience cyber-traveling and gain valuable knowledge about tourism and cultural heritage. Implementing such video games globally, featuring historical or touristic sceneries of Uzbekistan, can significantly boost the number of foreign visitors and tourists. This can foster cultural exchange and stimulate the country's economy. The aim of this research is to underscore the importance of video games in stimulating interest in tourism and cultural heritage in Uzbekistan. The increasing number of video game players worldwide reflects the growing popularity of video games as a form of entertainment. However, video games serve a

broader purpose beyond recreation; they can enhance intellectual thinking by providing facts and figures, acting as brain boosters or educational tools. Given their popularity, particularly among younger demographics, video games are an ideal medium for educational purposes. There has been a trend towards the development of more complex, serious games that combine pedagogical and entertaining elements. These games, including those designed to support cultural heritage purposes such as historical teaching and learning or enhancing museum visits, contribute to the educational landscape. The introduction of serious games reflects the widespread use of computer games with complex virtual worlds for entertainment. Video games have the potential to serve as powerful tools for promoting tourism development and preserving cultural heritage. By incorporating historical and touristic elements into gaming experiences, countries like Uzbekistan can attract more visitors and showcase their cultural richness to a global audience.

Table 1:

The number of game players in four continents

No:	Continents	The number of video game players
1.	Asia	1.48 billion
2.	Europe	715 million
3.	Latin America	420 million
4.	North America	285 million

Note: These statistics were conducted by Josh Howarth (August 10, 2023)

The mentioned statistics highlight the substantial number of people globally who play video games and share their opinions about them on social media platforms. Trustyou (2015) conducted a survey revealing that travelers often seek out other travelers' opinions before visiting a destination. Wang & Alasuutari (2017) further emphasized the influential role of fellow travelers' content in inspiring tourists, with over 20% of international tourists relying on online platforms for information. Real-world map-based video games could serve as such online platforms, enabling travelers to learn about city maps, cultural heritage, and history while providing an engaging experience.

Italy has implemented mini-video games designed to boost tourism by facilitating travel and imparting historical and cultural knowledge through gaming. According to Leotta et al. (2018), Serious Games (SG) are educational games that blend entertainment with instruction, enabling users to learn cultural content in an engaging manner. These games aim to spread knowledge about art, history, and culture, leveraging Information and Communication Technologies to enhance tourists' experiences. NEPTIS Polies system, as described by Leotta et al. (2018), streamlines the tourist experience by offering accessible information via a single Google map, eliminating the need for multiple mobile applications. The system also organizes national-level game competitions, promoting cultural exploration on a broader scale. NEPTIS Polies offers four mini-video games tailored to different age groups and interests. The "Treasure Hunt" game targets children, encouraging museum visits by collecting cards featuring cultural assets. "Visit Them All" challenges young audiences and adults to explore historical sites nationwide, earning medals for each site visited. The "Mysterious Path" game appeals to older players, guiding them through puzzles based on Italian history and myths. For those less familiar with gaming, the "Cultural Advisor" serves as a portable encyclopedia of Italian cultural sites. Additionally, players are incentivized with real prizes, promotions, or discounts to further encourage participation and exploration. Popularizing similar mini-video games in Uzbekistan could stimulate interest in

ancient monuments, historical sites, and cultural heritage among tourists and locals alike. These games offer accurate information about Uzbekistan's history and can also increase museum visitation, particularly among younger generations, by offering enticing rewards and incentives. Through such initiatives, Uzbekistan can leverage gaming technology to showcase its cultural treasures and attract more visitors.

Figure 2. NEPTIS Polies home page

Figure 3. Treasure hunt mini-gam

Figure 4. Visit them all mini-game

Figure 5. Mysterious paths mini-game

Figure 6. Cultural advisor mini-game

Note: These pictures are cited in “Encouraging persons to visit cultural sites through mini-games” by Leotta et al., (2018)

Utilizing online real-world map-based video games can serve as a pivotal tool in enhancing tourism and expanding people's understanding of cities from the comfort of their homes. Porecca (2020, as cited in K. Eskidmir & S. Kubat, 2021) contends that by closely examining city maps, video game level designs can create an expansive virtual space. In these games, players traverse through fictional or real-world environments, ranging from small residential areas to vast cityscapes, experiencing a sense of reality within the game. Games like "Watch Dogs: Legion" (depicting the map of London) and "Tom Clancy's The Division 2" by Ubisoft (featuring the map of Washington) exemplify how players can explore every corner of a city within the game, facilitating their familiarity with the city's layout and landmarks. This familiarity can prove invaluable in navigating the cities effectively in real life. Different gameplay approaches in these games encourage players to explore the streets and immerse themselves in the life and culture of the virtual environment (Eskidmir, 2021). With the widespread use of mobile phones, most individuals possess devices equipped with sensors that can enhance such gaming experiences. These sensors, including the Global Positioning System (GPS), enable devices to accurately determine their real-world locations within a few meters. Moreover, the internet provides access to various web Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) that offer real-time information about locations (Leorke, 2018). Handheld Augmented Reality (HAR) technology has demonstrated its effectiveness in facilitating learning about real-world places (Wang et al., 2012). Online real-world map-based video games offer a dynamic and immersive platform for individuals to explore cities virtually, enhancing their understanding of urban environments and potentially influencing their real-life interactions with these cities. Through the integration of mobile phone sensors and HAR technology, these gaming experiences can provide valuable insights into real-world locations, contributing to both entertainment and education.

Figure 7. The map of “Watch Dogs: Legion” .
London, England

Figure 8. The map of “Tom Clancy’s The
Division 2”. Washington, U.S.

Integrating the maps of famous tourist cities in Uzbekistan, such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, or Tashkent, into video games can significantly raise awareness of the country's historical destinations among travelers worldwide. These video games can serve as virtual guides, providing travelers with detailed information about these cities and assisting them in navigating their way through the country. Location-based games (LBGs) are particularly useful for tourists visiting Uzbekistan, as they utilize the player's physical location to modify the game status during gameplay, effectively blending the real and virtual worlds (De Souza e Silva and Sutko, 2011). LBGs are distinguished by their emphasis on physical activity in outdoor, public spaces, with gameplay mechanics facilitated by position-tracking technology (Ahlqvist, 2018). Utilizing location-aware technologies and portable devices like smartphones, LBGs enable players to explore real-world environments while engaging with digital content (De Souza e Silva and Sutko, 2009; Leorke, 2018). In Uzbekistan, LBGs can showcase the country's diverse destinations and cultural heritage, allowing players to immerse themselves in the game atmosphere and uncover hidden treasures and puzzles throughout various locations. These games not only entertain but also educate players about Uzbekistan's rich history, culture, and geography, thereby promoting tourism and fostering cultural exchange. By leveraging GPS technology and mobile devices, players can learn more about famous cities and countryside, contributing to the country's economy and increasing the likelihood of cultural interaction. Encouraging tourism through online video games presents a unique opportunity to not only attract more visitors but also enhance their understanding and appreciation of touristic places. With the widespread popularity of online video games, leveraging this medium can significantly boost the profitability of the tourism business and highlight lesser-known historical and cultural sites. Video games serve not only as sources of entertainment but also as platforms for spreading knowledge and inspiring players to explore new destinations and pursue their dreams.

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